

GENDER DIMENSION GUIDANCE FOR HORIZON EUROPE PROPOSALS

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1. Executive summary

Since the inception of Horizon Europe one of the required elements for any EU proposal is the **integration of the gender dimension into R&I content**. This section is – unless otherwise specified in the call – mandatory, and will be assessed under the Excellence award criterion. (as seen in Figure 1, a snapshot from the general application template¹)

- Describe how the gender dimension (i.e. sex and/or gender analysis) is taken into account in the project's research and innovation content [e.g. 1 page]. If you do not consider such a gender dimension to be relevant in your project, please provide a justification.

⚠ *Note: This section is mandatory except for topics which have been identified in the work programme as not requiring the integration of the gender dimension into R&I content.*

⚠ *Remember that that this question relates to the content of the planned research and innovation activities, and not to gender balance in the teams in charge of carrying out the project.*

⚠ *Sex and gender analysis refers to biological characteristics and social/cultural factors respectively. For guidance on methods of sex / gender analysis and the issues to be taken into account, please refer to https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/gendered-innovations-2-2020-nov-24_en*

Figure 1. Standard application form indicating the gender dimension requirement.

As a consultancy company, AMIRES is committed to supporting the development of strong, competitive proposals under Horizon Europe and other funding programmes. Addressing gender balance thoughtfully in both consortium composition and research content can significantly strengthen the quality and impact of a proposal. Beyond scientific excellence and innovation, today's research landscape demands attention to social impact, inclusiveness, and equality. To advance these goals, AMIRES has established the Gender Equality Board (GEB) within the company, which is dedicated to is cross-checking all proposals prior to submission. Therefore, we would like to share basic information as a guidance when preparing proposals for submission.

However, these elements continue to be relevant even once the project has been funded and enters the implementation period.

Based on our broad experience and expertise in proposal preparation, this document provides practical recommendations and a checklist to support you when writing a proposal and defining the gender dimension of your research and innovation activities. The goal is to make it easier for coordinators and partners to integrate gender aspects in a way that is relevant, credible, and aligned with funding programme requirements, while also strengthening the overall quality and impact of the project.

¹ [Standard Application Form \(HE RIA, IA\)](#)

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2. Introduction

Although much progress has been made in recent decades, Europe's research and innovation sectors continues to be male-dominated.

- At the EU level, only **34% of researchers are women**
- **In terms of career advancement, women are disadvantaged** and occupy only 24% of grade A positions in natural sciences and a mere 19% in engineering and technology, fields critical for Europe's global competitiveness
- Only **16% of authorship teams** are gender-balanced
- **Gender inequalities become more pronounced with seniority**: women represent 48% of early-stage authors but only 36% of senior-stage authors
- **Women are severely underrepresented in Innovation landscape**, accounting for just **9% of inventors** - a number unchanged in over a decade
- **Research remains largely gender-blind** with 98% of EU publications at the EU level which do not include a gender dimension (i.e., sex or gender analysis)
- **Women are also underrepresented in decision-making roles**: At the EU level, women represent only 26% of heads of higher education institutions, 22% of university presidencies, and 38% of board memberships²

For this reason, the European Commission has repeatedly affirmed its commitment to gender equality in research and innovation made it a cross-cutting priority in Horizon Europe programme with the introduction of strengthened provisions. Among them is the **integration of a gender dimension into research and innovation content** - a requirement by default, unless explicitly specified otherwise.

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en, accessed 15.08.2025

3. Sex and Gender in EU proposals

Considering gender dimension aspects is a part of broad of activities which seek to reach gender equality. Firstly, and most importantly: The gender dimension is more than gender balanced teams. In general, the "gender dimension in R&I" and "sex/gender analysis" are often as synonyms in EU policy on gender equality in R&I. Both refer to the inclusion of **gender considerations in the research content, such as the research design, study implementation, scientific reporting, and general science communication.**

Figure 2. Context and content of gender³.

As of January 2025, 80.5% of all Horizon Europe topics (RIA, IA, COFUND) – in absolute numbers 977 out of 1 214 topics - integrate the gender dimension in their content.⁴

³ Adapted from [Sex and Gender in Research_Maribor.pdf](#)

⁴ **Key figures from Horizon Europe: R&I monitoring flash.** Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission). 06 March 2025. Available here: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6c9f5a3b-fa43-11ef-b7db-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

4. Key definitions

Understanding the distinctions between sex, gender, and intersectionality is essential for conducting inclusive and socially aware research. These concepts are often mistakenly used interchangeably, yet they influence individuals' experiences in very different ways.

Key Definitions

Source: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/gender-eu-research-and-innovation_en

Figure 3. Key definitions regarding Gender dimensions

5. Importance of considerations of gender aspects

Overall, the idea behind the inclusion of Gender Dimension in EU funding proposals is to get researchers in all fields to start thinking about **how gender impacts their work**, which has not previously been considered in many areas. Over time, this will lead to **better awareness** of the impact of unconscious gender bias on the policies, decisions and activities of institutions and businesses as well as to help identify needs and to develop practical solutions that work for everyone. This is part of the "Fix the knowledge" approach to gender equality over the past several decades (see next figure):

Three Strategic Approaches taken by governments and universities to improve gender equality

Source: <https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/what-is-gendered-innovations.html>

Figure 4. Three strategic approaches to improve gender equality.

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In particular, incorporating gender aspects and gender-sensitive approaches into research and innovation through a thorough consideration of sex and gender aspects as well as intersecting factors in the design and delivery of R&I is necessary for the following reasons:

- If R&I activities are not organised to address biological sex and gender, datasets and insights generated will be biased, which might result in unfair approaches or strategies, flawed methodologies, incomplete conclusions, and prolongation of gender inequalities.
- We should no longer assume that drugs, devices, interventions, and policies are equally appropriate for men and women. All these require a meticulous analysis and involvement of both female and male participants to avoid the risk of causing unintended harm.
- Biological sex and gender are critical determinants of health and behaviour, and a significant variable which should be considered thoroughly in order for project results contribute to a more inclusive and equitable scientific community.
- Consideration of sex and gender aspects will improve the scientific quality and generalizability of the generated knowledge and produce a better societal significance of the produced knowledge, technology and/or innovation. This will ultimately lead to goods and services which are better suited to the needs of all people, and the creation of innovations that better serve society as a whole.
- Overall, this will create significant added value of the research in terms of excellence, creativity and business opportunity.

Gender influences how individuals experience health, education, employment, technology, and countless other domains. Therefore, the integration of gender dimension should not only be seen as a checkbox to tick off in the proposal, but as a real chance to achieving excellence and relevance, improve the quality and applicability of your work, uncover hidden biases, and contribute to more inclusive and impactful results.

Sex, Gender and Intersectional Analysis has the potential to enhance all phases of research:

Source: <https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/what-is-gendered-innovations.html>

Figure 5. Sex, Gender and Intersectional Analysis.

Additionally, we observe that increasingly, the gender dimension in R&I is expanding towards integration of an **intersectional perspective** in the content of R&I as well. This means that not only women's and men's biological characteristics (sex), but also intersex persons and the – changing – social and cultural features (gender) of women, men and non-binary and transgender people and other relevant social and cultural factors will be considered.

6. Recommendations

But what does this mean in practice, and what to consider when writing this part of your Horizon Europe proposal? Based on our broad experience and expertise, here's what we recommend:

- **Start with an examination of how sex and gender influence your research topic**, e.g. by reviewing existing literature to identify gender disparities. This might be more straightforward in some areas, such as healthcare, education and employment, but even seemingly 'neutral' fields such as industry, energy, sustainability may have different impacts on women and men and may inadvertently perpetuate inequality or discrimination.
- **Acknowledge these shortcomings and apply these insights and identified gaps into your project idea**, e.g. by incorporating them into your research questions and project objectives and committing to inquiring further about the correlation of your research topic with sex and gender when planning and carrying out your EU funded project.
- **Take the gender dimension into account when planning and implementing activities at various levels in the proposed project**, such as in theoretical background, methodology, impact, work package activities and dissemination.
- **Describe how you will ensure to provide the project outcome to all members of society without discrimination of any personal characteristics** such as sex, gender, age or race and how the gender dimension is carefully integrated at various levels in the proposed project, such as in theoretical background, methodology, impact, and dissemination sections. For instance, by collecting, characterising, analysing, reporting and publishing sex- and gender-based data.
- **Ensure your proposal clearly articulates how integrating gender analysis will enhance the scientific rigor, relevance, and inclusivity of your research**. Explain how your chosen approach will help uncover gender-specific needs, behaviors, or outcomes, and how addressing these differences can lead to more equitable and impactful solutions. Additionally, demonstrate how your work contributes to reducing structural inequalities and promoting social cohesion across Europe.
- **Cross-check this section with a diverse group of people** to make sure a wide range of perspectives are considered. This can include individuals of different genders, cultural backgrounds, disciplines, and lived experience. This collaborative review process can help identify potential blind spots, challenge assumptions, and strengthen the inclusivity and relevance of your proposal. It also demonstrates a commitment to co-creation and participatory approaches, which are increasingly valued in European research and innovation frameworks.

If you do not consider such a gender dimension to be relevant in your project, you should provide a justification. However, this is rarely the case, as sex and gender play a role in all aspects of life and science. Therefore, AMIRES explicitly supports the EU efforts in making sure that gender dimension aspects in R&I content are considered in all EU funded projects.

In addition, to the above, we also recommend that all consortium partners follow the “four As” of research impact assessment with regard to gender equality:

Four “As” of research impact assessment to address gender bias in research

Source: Ovseiko, P.V., Greenhalgh, T., Adam, P. et al. A global call for action to include gender in research impact assessment. *Health Res Policy Sys* 14, 50 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-016-0126-z>

Figure 6. Four: “As” or research impact assessment.

7. Summary and checklist

Consider fulfilling the following list as a checklist when writing a proposal and defining the gender dimension of the research and innovation.

- 1. Assess Gender Relevance**
Examine how sex and gender influence the research topic and its context.
- 2. Identify and Address Gaps**
Acknowledge existing shortcomings and incorporate insights and identified gaps into the project concept.
- 3. Integrate Gender in Project Planning**
Ensure gender considerations are embedded in the planning and implementation of activities at all levels.
- 4. Promote Inclusive Outcomes**
Describe how project outcomes will be made accessible to all members of society, without discrimination based on personal characteristics.
- 5. Highlight the Value of Gender Analysis**
Clearly articulate how gender analysis enhances research quality and contributes to reducing inequalities across Europe.
- 6. Engage Diverse Perspectives**
Review this section with a diverse group to ensure multiple viewpoints are considered and represented.

In the competitive Horizon Europe funding landscape, **embedding a compelling gender dimension can help you stand out among other excellent proposals.** We hope that this guide could help you point thinking about this topic.

In addition to this, remember that gender equality, especially in terms of WP leaders and researchers, can be an also become a tie-breaker criteria, and that a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) an eligibility criterion for all higher education establishments, research organisations, as well as public bodies from Member States and Associated Countries.

8. Key resources

If you want to learn more, check out our favourite resources on the topic:

- **Overview of Gender in EU research and innovation:** https://rea.ec.europa.eu/gender-eu-research-and-innovation_en
 - **“Gendered Innovations” portal** hosted by Stanford University: <https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/>
 - **EU report “Gendered innovations - How gender analysis contributes to research: report of the expert group ‘Innovation through gender’”** <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d15a85d6-cd2d-4fbc-b998-42e53a73a449/language-en>
 - **EU Report “Gendered innovations 2: How inclusive analysis contributes to research and innovation”** <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/33b4c99f-2e66-11eb-b27b-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
 - **EU’s Gender equality strategy:** https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality/gender-equality-strategy_en
- European Institute for Gender Equality:** <https://eige.europa.eu/>